

In silico evaluation of the influence of N-alkylation and halogenation on isatin Schiff bases as potential inhibitors of bacterial DNA gyrase*

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Abstract

Isatin Schiff bases are multifunctional pharmacophores with reported antimicrobial relevance, and structural modifications such as halogenation and N-alkylation may influence their interaction with bacterial targets. In this docking-based study, a focused series of 20 3-[(pyridin-3-yl)imino]-1H-indole-2-one derivatives was designed to explore how halogen substitution and N-chloroalkylation affect the predicted binding of the isatin scaffold to the ATP-binding domain of *Staphylococcus aureus* DNA gyrase subunit B (PDB ID: 5CPH). The ligand set included non-alkylated analogs and N-(2-chloroethyl), N-(3-chloropropyl), and N-(3-chloroisobutyl) derivatives bearing fluorine, chlorine, bromine, or iodine substituents. Molecular docking predicted binding free energies ranging from -6.51 to -8.61 kcal/mol. Fluorination was most favorable in the non-alkylated series, whereas bromine and iodine became more beneficial in the presence of bulkier N-chloroalkyl substituents. The best-scoring compounds were stabilized mainly by hydrophobic and π -related contacts with Ile51, Ile86, Ile102, Ile175, and Leu103, together with hydrogen-bonding or water-mediated interactions involving Asp81, Asn54, Ser55, and Arg84. These results suggest that the effect of halogenation is context-dependent and influenced by the size and flexibility of the N-substituent. The study provides a preliminary docking-based structure-activity relationship (SAR) model for prioritizing isatin Schiff bases for further synthesis, enzymatic testing, and antibacterial evaluation, but the predicted affinities should not be interpreted as experimentally confirmed inhibitory activity.

Keywords

antibacterial potential, DNA gyrase, halogenation, isatin Schiff bases, molecular docking, N-alkylation, structure-activity relationship

Introduction

Antibacterial resistance has evolved from a medical issue into a global crisis with severe health, economic, and social consequences (Huemer et al. 2020). More than 1.27 million

people die annually from resistant infections, and projections suggest that this number could increase tenfold by 2050 without effective interventions (European Antimicrobial Resistance Collaborators 2022). Pathogens such as *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Klebsiella*

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pneumoniae, and *Acinetobacter baumannii* are among the most persistent causes of nosocomial infections, leading to longer hospitalizations, higher costs, and increased mortality (van Hecke et al. 2017; Mancuso et al. 2021). The urgent demand for new antibacterial agents is challenged by the long, costly process of traditional drug development (O'Brien 2015; Biala et al. 2023). Consequently, research has increasingly focused on computer-aided drug design, which enables virtual screening and activity prediction of diverse chemical scaffolds prior to synthesis (Chang et al. 2022; Giordano et al. 2022; Wu et al. 2024).

Among the many structures studied, isatin (1H-indole-2,3-dione) stands out as a particularly valuable pharmacophore (Cheke et al. 2022). This relatively small molecule serves as a core for a wide range of biologically active compounds (Shu et al. 2025). Isatin derivatives are characterized by antimicrobial, antitumor, anti-inflammatory, antiviral, and neuroprotective activity, which makes them attractive targets for molecular design (Beula et al. 2021). Their structural flexibility offers wide opportunities for optimization of their pharmacological properties (Esam et al. 2022; Hassan et al. 2023). Comparative studies have shown that small changes in the electron density of the isatin core can drastically change its affinity for bacterial enzymes (Ferraz de Paiva et al. 2021). At the same time, modifications at the N1 position, such as N-alkylation, affect lipophilicity, spatial orientation, and penetration through the cell membrane. Thus, the two strategies—halogenation and alkylation—are often considered complementary in optimizing antibacterial activity (Varun et al. 2019). However, their combined effect on binding to enzymes such as DNA gyrase remains insufficiently studied, which opens a field for in-depth molecular analysis.

As one of the central enzymes in the bacterial DNA replication process, DNA gyrase represents an established and highly specific therapeutic target (Khan et al. 2018). Many classical antibacterial agents, such as fluoroquinolones, exert their action precisely by interacting with this enzyme. The problem is that most known inhibitors are already affected by increasing resistance, making the discovery of new structural types of ligands of paramount importance (Coba-Males et al. 2023). The present study fits precisely into this logic. Through a combination of structural design and molecular docking, this study evaluates how halogenation and N-alkylation affect the predicted binding behavior of isatin Schiff bases within the ATP-binding domain of *Staphylococcus aureus* DNA gyrase subunit B (PDB ID: 5CPH).

To date, no study has systematically investigated how halogenation and N-alkylation in combination modulate the binding of isatin Schiff bases to GyrB. Existing publications have examined these modifications individually, but not in the context of a controlled structure–activity relationship (SAR) assay that combines four halogens (F, Cl, Br, and I) with four variants of N-alkyl substituents with increasing steric demands. This 4 × 4 matrix design allows a unique investigation of the synergistic and compensatory effects between halogen polarizability and N-alkyl steric

bulk—factors that are not considered together in known classes of GyrB inhibitors, such as aminocoumarins, benzamides, or fluoroquinolones. Therefore, the present study provides a comparative docking model suggesting that dual electronic–steric tuning of the isatin backbone may influence ligand accommodation within the GyrB pocket and the pattern of interactions in the active site.

Materials and methods

Ligand dataset preparation

A series of 20 3-[(pyridin-3-yl)imino]-1H-indole-2-one derivatives were virtually designed as the target ligands for molecular docking analysis. The dataset included the non-alkylated scaffold and three N-alkylated analogs in which the alkyl substituent carries a terminal chlorine atom (N-(2-chloroethyl), N-(3-chloropropyl), and N-(3-chloroisobutyl)) with four halogen substituents (fluorine, chlorine, bromine, and iodine) introduced at the aromatic ring of the isatin moiety. The general structure of the designed isatin derivatives and the variation of substituents at positions R₁ and R₂ are presented in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. General structure of the designed isatin Schiff base derivatives with variable halogen substitution at the aromatic ring (R₁ = F, Cl, Br, I) and N-chloroalkyl substituents at position N¹ (R₂ = -CH₂CH₂Cl, -CH₂CH₂CH₂Cl, -CH₂CH(CH₃)CH₂Cl).

Preparation of compounds for molecular docking

The 3D structures of all ligands were constructed using Avogadro 1.2.0 (Hanwell et al. 2012). Each compound underwent geometric optimization using Avogadro's "Optimize Geometry" function. The optimized molecules were then saved in MOL2 format, and the corresponding files were prepared in AutoDock Tools by adding polar hydrogens, assigning Gasteiger charges, detecting rotatable bonds, and setting the torsional degrees of freedom (Morris et al. 2009).

Target protein preparation

The crystal structure of the ATP-binding domain of *Staphylococcus aureus* GyrB (PDB ID: 5CPH) was obtained from the RCSB Protein Data Bank (Berman et al. 2000). Initial preprocessing was performed in UCSF ChimeraX 1.6 (Read et al. 2024), where all non-standard residues were removed. Subsequently, in AutoDock Tools, missing

side chains were checked and repaired where necessary, polar hydrogens were added, and Kollman charges were assigned according to the AD4 specification. The processed structure was saved in PDBQT format and served as the receptor for all docking simulations. The side chains of Asn54, Asp81, Arg84, Glu85, Ile86, Ile102, and Arg144 were defined as flexible during docking to account for local conformational adjustments within the ATP-binding pocket (Mesleh et al. 2016). These residues are directly involved in ligand recognition and stabilization of the nucleotide or inhibitor through hydrogen bonding (Asp81, Asn54, and Arg84) and hydrophobic interactions. Allowing their torsional freedom improves the accuracy of docking poses by reflecting the natural adaptability of the binding site during ligand accommodation.

Molecular docking setup

Flexible ligand docking was performed using AutoDock 4.2 with the Lamarckian Genetic Algorithm. The receptor was treated as semi-flexible: selected side chains within the ATP-binding pocket were defined as flexible, whereas the remaining protein structure was kept rigid. For each ligand–enzyme pair, 100 independent docking runs were performed. The grid box was centered on the ATP-binding domain at $x = 5.91$, $y = 2.26$, and $z = -1.65$ Å and was adjusted to encompass the catalytic pocket. The grid dimensions were $60 \times 60 \times 60$ points, with a spacing of 0.375 Å. Each run involved a maximum of 25,000,000 energy evaluations, a population size of 300 individuals, a mutation rate of 0.02, and a crossover rate of 0.8. The best-ranked conformation was selected based on the lowest binding free energy.

Docking output analysis

Docking poses and protein–ligand interactions were analyzed using UCSF ChimeraX and BIOVIA Discovery Studio Visualizer v21.1.0.20298 (Baroroh et al. 2023). The analysis focused on binding energy, estimated inhibition constant, pose clustering, and non-covalent contacts within the ATP-binding pocket, including hydrogen bonding, hydro-

phobic interactions, π -related contacts, and halogen-associated interactions. Two-dimensional interaction maps were generated for representative ligand–receptor complexes to support the structural interpretation of the docking results.

Results and discussion

Validation of docking protocol and comparative binding analysis

To evaluate the suitability of the docking protocol for the ATP-binding pocket of *Staphylococcus aureus* DNA gyrase subunit B, the co-crystallized reference ligand from the 5CPH structure was redocked into the prepared receptor model (Table 1). The same docking parameters and search algorithm used for the designed isatin Schiff bases were applied during validation. The detailed scheme of the interactions of the reference ligand is presented in Fig. 2.

Flexible ligand docking was performed using AutoDock 4.2 with the Lamarckian Genetic Algorithm. The receptor was treated as semi-flexible, with selected ATP-binding-site side chains defined as flexible, whereas the remaining protein structure was kept rigid. The docking grid was centered on the ATP-binding pocket at $x = 5.91$, $y = 2.26$, and $z = -1.65$ Å, with grid dimensions of $60 \times 60 \times 60$ points and a spacing of 0.375 Å.

The redocked pose of the reference ligand reproduced the experimentally observed binding orientation with an RMSD below 2.0 Å, which is commonly used as an acceptable threshold for successful pose reproduction in docking validation. This result supports the suitability of the selected grid box and docking parameters for recovering the reference binding mode within the GyrB ATP-binding site. The corresponding interaction map of the redocked reference ligand is presented in Fig. 2.

The redocked reference ligand showed polar contacts involving Asp81, Ser55, and neighboring residues, together with hydrophobic or π -related contacts involving Ile86, Ile102, and Leu103. These residues partially overlapped with those predicted to interact with the designed isatin

Table 1. Redocking validation parameters for the AutoDock 4.2 docking protocol.

Parameter	Description
Protein structure	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> DNA gyrase subunit B ATP-binding domain
PDB ID	5CPH
Validation ligand	Co-crystallized reference ligand from 5CPH
Docking software	AutoDock 4.2
Search algorithm	Lamarckian Genetic Algorithm
Docking type	Flexible ligand docking with semi-flexible receptor treatment
Flexible receptor residues	Asn54, Asp81, Arg84, Glu85, Ile86, Ile102, and Arg144
Grid center	$x = 5.91$, $y = 2.26$, $z = -1.65$ Å
Grid dimensions	$60 \times 60 \times 60$
Grid spacing	0.375 Å
Validation criterion	RMSD ≤ 2.0 Å between crystallographic and redocked pose
Redocking result	RMSD = 1.43 Å
Interpretation	The protocol reproduced the reference binding orientation within the ATP-binding pocket

Figure 2. Two-dimensional interaction map of the reference ligand redocked into the ATP-binding center of *Staphylococcus aureus* DNA gyrase subunit B (PDB ID: 5CPH), showing the main hydrogen and hydrophobic contacts with the catalytic residues.

Schiff bases, supporting the use of the selected ATP-binding pocket for comparative docking analysis.

However, this validation demonstrates only that the protocol can reproduce the crystallographic binding pose of the reference ligand under the applied docking conditions. It does not establish the quantitative accuracy of the predicted binding energies, nor does it confirm the biological activity or dynamic stability of the designed ligand–GyrB complexes. Therefore, the docking results were interpreted comparatively within the studied ligand series and used for structure-guided prioritization rather than as experimentally validated measures of inhibitory potency.

Series 1: Non-alkylated derivatives

In the first series, Schiff bases without chloroalkyl substituents at the N1 position were studied, with the aim of assessing the net effect of halogenation on the affinity for DNA gyrase subunit B. The results obtained showed that all halogenated derivatives were characterized by negative binding energy values, ranging from -8.06 to -8.61 kcal/mol, which suggests favorable predicted accommodation within the enzyme binding pocket. The results are summarized in Table 2, and the corresponding ligand codes (L01–L05) refer to the non-alkylated isatin Schiff base derivatives bearing hydrogen, fluorine,

chlorine, bromine, and iodine substituents at position C5 of the isatin ring, respectively.

The lowest energy and, accordingly, the lowest inhibition constant value were reported for the fluorinated derivative L02, which showed an approximately 2.5-fold improvement in calculated K_i relative to the non-halogenated analog. The derivatives containing chlorine (L03) and bromine (L04) showed similar binding energy values, while a slight decrease in affinity was observed for the iodinated derivative (L05), comparable to that of the parent structure.

The obtained data outline a trend in which fluorine has the most favorable effect on the interaction with the enzyme, while heavier halogens do not lead to further improvement. This discrepancy with the expected “weight-dependent” dependence can be explained by steric constraints in the active pocket of the enzyme, which is relatively narrow and hydrophobic. The presence of bulkier substituents such as $-Br$ and $-I$ probably creates steric strain or restricts the optimal orientation of the ligand, which is reflected in the higher RMSD values (7.7 Å for L04 and 7.8 Å for L05). At the same time, L02, although with a slightly increased RMSD, retained favorable docking energetics, suggesting that fluorination may support energetically acceptable binding orientations within the catalytic site.

The intermolecular energy follows the same trend—lowest for L02, indicating that the improvement in affinity stems

Table 2. Binding parameters and conformational analysis for non-alkylated isatin Schiff bases (L01–L05) with DNA gyrase subunit B (PDB ID: 5CPH).

Ligand ID	L01	L02	L03	L04	L05
Conformations	11	2	3	1	2
RMSD from reference structure, Å	4.766	6.148	5.304	7.719	7.761
Binding energy, kcal/mol	-8.06	-8.61	-8.26	-8.24	-8.12
Inhibition constant, K_i	1.23 μ M	491.33 nM	880.30 nM	914.16 nM	1.12 μ M
Intermolecular energy, kcal/mol	-8.36	-8.90	-8.56	-8.54	-8.42
Total internal energy, kcal/mol	-14.79	-14.12	-12.69	-13.86	-13.34
Torsional free energy, kcal/mol	$+0.30$	$+0.30$	$+0.30$	$+0.30$	$+0.30$
Unbound energy, kcal/mol	-14.79	-14.12	-12.69	-13.86	-13.34

primarily from stronger dispersion and electrostatic interactions. All compounds have the same value of torsional free energy (+0.30 kcal/mol), which excludes the possibility that the differences in ΔG stem from different ligand flexibility. This means that the observed changes in energetics are mainly due to electronic effects and not conformational entropy.

In terms of conformational stability, L01 forms the most numerous and compact clusters, suggesting a more homogeneous binding pattern. After halogenation, the number of clusters decreases significantly, and only one pose is observed for the brominated derivative, suggesting a stronger dependence on a specific orientation and lower convergence of the docking results.

Overall, this series shows that fluorination appeared to be the most favorable modification within this non-alkylated docking series. The most likely explanation is related to an electronic “fine-tuning” effect induced by fluorination of the isatin π -system, which improves the orientation of the aromatic core and enhances π - σ and dispersion interactions with hydrophobic residues such as Ile86. In addition, the electron withdrawal exerted by fluorine may stabilize water-mediated hydrogen bonds

involving polar residues such as Asp81 and Ser55. On the other hand, chlorine and bromine provide only modest enhancement, and iodine does not make a significant contribution, which is likely due to a combination of steric and orientational factors.

Therefore, within the non-alkylated skeleton, fluorine appears to be a favorable electronic modifier in this specific scaffold context. To complement the numerical docking data, 2D interaction diagrams were generated to illustrate the spatial organization and type of non-covalent contacts within the GyrB active site, as shown in Fig. 3. These visualizations provide structural support for the observed affinity trends and clarify the influence of halogen substitution and N-alkylation on ligand accommodation and stability.

Series 2: N-(2-chloroethyl) derivatives

The second series includes Schiff bases alkylated at the N1 position with a 2-chloroethyl group. The results show a general decrease in predicted affinity compared with the non-alkylated analogs, which is due to the increased torsional flexibility and slight steric effect of the chloroethyl group. However, the observed energetics indicate that

Figure 3. Interaction maps of non-alkylated isatin Schiff bases (L01–L05) docked in the ATP-binding site of DNA gyrase subunit B (PDB ID: 5CPH).

this effect can be partially compensated by appropriate halogenation. The results are summarized in Table 3, and the corresponding ligand codes (L06–L10) refer to the N-(2-chloroethyl) isatin Schiff base derivatives bearing hydrogen, fluorine, chlorine, bromine, and iodine substituents at position C5 of the isatin ring, respectively.

The energy values range from -7.38 to -8.10 kcal/mol, with the lowest energy and smallest inhibition constant reported for the brominated analog L09. It demonstrates approximately a 2.7-fold improvement in potency over the non-halogenated standard. The fluorinated derivative (L07) follows, which also shows a moderately increased affinity. The chlorinated analog (L08) is characterized by weaker activity, and the iodinated analog (L10) by the highest binding energy. Thus, bromine appeared to be the most favorable substituent in this docking series. Iodine was associated with a less favorable docking profile, possibly due to combined electronic and steric effects.

Comparison with the non-alkylated derivatives clearly highlights the impact of the N-(2-chloroethyl) group. For most halogenated analogs, a deterioration in energetics of approximately $+0.7$ kcal/mol is observed, which corresponds to increased torsional free energy. This universal energetic penalty is due to greater flexibility and the need for partial geometric reorganization upon binding. Only for L09 is this negative trend minimal, suggesting a possible synergy between the electronic polarizability of bromine and the moderate steric bulk of the N-(2-chloroethyl) group.

Conformational analysis also supports this conclusion. The brominated derivative exhibits the best convergence (five conformations) and a moderate RMSD

(6.16 Å), suggesting a more consistent predicted binding orientation. L07 and L08 each form three conformations with RMSDs between 6.4 and 8.6 Å, while L10 shows the highest variability (RMSD = 9.56 Å) and only one reliable pose, which casts doubt on its stability in the active site.

The binding energy decomposition confirms that the differences in total free energy are mainly due to intermolecular interactions. For all analogs, the torsional component is constant, and the change in ΔG correlates directly with the intermolecular energy: $-H -8.40 < -F -8.80 < -Cl -8.45 < -Br -9.00 < -I -8.27$ kcal/mol. These values indicate that bromine optimally fills the hydrophobic cavity, probably by making more intensive alkyl or π -alkyl contacts with residues such as Ile51, Leu103, and Ile175. By contrast, the iodinated analog shows weaker affinity and a higher RMSD, suggesting suboptimal accommodation and an increased orientational penalty despite its higher polarizability. The 2D interaction plots, presented in Fig. 4, provide a detailed depiction of the non-covalent binding pattern within the GyrB active site.

Series 3: N-(3-chloropropyl) derivatives

The third series includes isatin Schiff bases alkylated at the N1 position with a 3-chloropropyl group, a modification that adds significant steric bulk and increases the internal flexibility of the molecule. As a result, there is an overall decrease in predicted affinity compared with the non-alkylated and N-(2-chloroethyl) derivatives, although heavier halogens appeared to partially compensate for this effect in the docking model. The results are summarized in Table 4. The corresponding ligand codes (L11–L15) refer to the N-(3-chloropropyl) isatin

Table 3. Binding parameters and conformational analysis for N-(2-chloroethyl) isatin Schiff bases (L06–L10) with DNA gyrase subunit B (PDB ID: 5CPH).

Ligand ID	L06	L07	L08	L09	L10
Conformations	1	3	3	5	1
RMSD from reference structure, Å	4.726	6.389	8.613	6.156	9.564
Binding energy, kcal/mol	-7.51	-7.91	-7.56	-8.10	-7.38
Inhibition constant, Ki	3.15 μ M	1.60 μ M	2.89 μ M	1.15 μ M	3.89 μ M
Intermolecular energy, kcal/mol	-8.40	-8.80	-8.45	-9.00	-8.27
Total internal energy, kcal/mol	-13.29	-13.35	-12.60	-13.90	-13.92
Torsional free energy, kcal/mol	+0.89	+0.89	+0.89	+0.89	+0.89
Unbound energy, kcal/mol	-13.29	-13.35	-12.60	-13.90	-13.92

Table 4. Binding parameters and conformational analysis for N-(3-chloropropyl) isatin Schiff bases (L11–L15) with DNA gyrase subunit B (PDB ID: 5CPH).

Ligand ID	L11	L12	L13	L14	L15
Conformations	4	3	3	4	3
RMSD from reference structure, Å	10.690	11.240	4.616	10.693	9.301
Binding energy, kcal/mol	-6.86	-7.17	-7.57	-7.50	-7.77
Inhibition constant, Ki	9.41 μ M	5.56 μ M	2.82 μ M	3.21 μ M	2.02 μ M
Intermolecular energy, kcal/mol	-8.05	-8.36	-8.76	-8.69	-8.96
Total internal energy, kcal/mol	-15.52	-12.60	-10.55	-12.36	-14.24
Torsional free energy, kcal/mol	+1.19	+1.19	+1.19	+1.19	+1.19
Unbound energy, kcal/mol	-15.52	-12.60	-10.55	-12.36	-14.24

Figure 4. Interaction maps of N-(2-chloroethyl) isatin Schiff bases (L06–L10) docked in the ATP-binding site of DNA gyrase subunit B (PDB ID: 5CPH).

Schiff base derivatives bearing hydrogen, fluorine, chlorine, bromine, and iodine substituents at position C5 of the isatin ring, respectively.

The binding energy values show a clear trend: increasing the atomic mass of the halogen improves the affinity. The non-halogenated analog (L11) has the weakest activity ($\Delta G = -6.86$ kcal/mol; $K_i = 9.41$ μM), while the iodinated derivative (L15) reaches the lowest binding energy ($\Delta G = -7.77$ kcal/mol; $K_i = 2.02$ μM), representing an approximately fourfold improvement in the inhibition constant. However, despite this apparent improvement, the corresponding RMSD values remain relatively high (approximately 9–11 Å), suggesting that the observed gain in binding energy might reflect conformational variability rather than a more reliable or experimentally relevant binding mode within the active pocket. Fluorination leads to a modest improvement (-7.17 kcal/mol; $K_i = 5.56$ μM), and the chlorinated and brominated analogs occupy an intermediate position with similar ΔG values (-7.57 and -7.50 kcal/mol, respectively). Thus, a pattern emerges in which halogen polarizability appears to be an important factor for stabilizing the ligand in the active center, while smaller substituents do not provide sufficient dispersion interaction to counteract the increased torsional energy generated by the N-(3-chloropropyl)

chain. Overall, the docking scores obtained for this series suggest moderate predicted affinity toward GyrB, consistent with non-covalent interactions characteristic of reversible inhibitors.

In the context of the other series, the N-(3-chloropropyl) derivatives demonstrate the highest torsional free energy values (+1.19 kcal/mol), confirming that increasing the alkyl length at the N1 position significantly increases the internal flexibility and reduces the degree of conformational locking upon binding. In this sense, the slight improvement in L15 can be explained by a compensatory effect due to more pronounced π - σ and π -alkyl dispersion interactions with hydrophobic residues (Ile86, Ile102, and Leu103) and stabilization of the complex by an extended network of water-mediated hydrogen bonds. These interactions probably compensate for the steric effect of the bulky iodine atom and maintain a relatively favorable binding energy. In contrast, fluorination, while effective for smaller N-substituents, is not sufficient to counteract the steric cost of the 3-chloropropyl group.

Conformational analysis reveals interesting patterns. All analogs form several energetically similar conformations (3–4), which indicates a dynamic but not chaotic binding profile. The lowest RMSD value is recorded for L13 (4.62 Å), which indicates a relatively stable and

repeatable orientation in the active site. Conversely, the fluorinated, brominated, and iodinated derivatives are characterized by higher RMSD values (9–11 Å), which probably reflects the existence of more than one possible binding mode or partial occupation of two subpockets within the ATP-binding site. However, the intermolecular energy values clearly show that these more “scattered” configurations are energetically more favorable, especially for iodine (−8.96 kcal/mol).

The comparison between the chlorinated and iodinated derivatives highlights an interesting trade-off between geometric stability and energetic optimization. While L13 exhibits a more compact and predictable arrangement in the active site, L15 combines greater polarizability with a slight orientation shift, allowing it to form tighter hydrophobic contacts. This difference in stabilization mechanism could explain why Cl and I have similar binding behavior but different energetics.

Fig. 5 illustrates the 2D interaction profiles between the studied ligands and the GyrB binding pocket, emphasizing key hydrogen bonding and hydrophobic contacts. The visual comparison complements the docking data, supporting the proposed structural interpretation of the predicted stabilization observed for selected halogenated and N-alkylated derivatives.

Series 4: N-(3-chloroisobutyl) derivatives

The last series of studies includes derivatives alkylated at the N1 position with a 3-chloroisobutyl moiety, a structural modification that combines a bulky steric effect with increased lipophilicity. This combination may affect the spatial organization of the molecule in the active site and the nature of interactions with amino acid residues. Docking results suggest that despite the expected torsional cost (+1.19 kcal/mol), the addition of a halogen substituent may partially or, in some cases, substantially compensate for the energetic penalty observed with smaller N-chloroalkyl groups. The results are summarized in Table 5, and the corresponding ligand codes (L16–L20) refer to the N-(3-chloroisobutyl) isatin Schiff base derivatives bearing hydrogen, fluorine, chlorine, bromine, and iodine substituents at position C5 of the isatin ring, respectively.

Among the compounds studied, the lowest binding energy was reported for the iodinated derivative L20 ($\Delta G = -8.45$ kcal/mol; $K_i = 0.64$ μM), which demonstrated an approximately 25-fold improvement in the inhibition constant compared with the non-halogenated analog ($\Delta G = -6.51$ kcal/mol; $K_i = 16.8$ μM). The brominated (L19) and chlorinated (L18) derivatives also showed favorable predicted binding energies ($\Delta G = -8.31$ and

Figure 5. Interaction maps of N-(3-chloropropyl) isatin Schiff bases (L11–L15) docked in the ATP-binding site of DNA gyrase subunit B (PDB ID: 5CPH).

Table 5. Binding parameters and conformational analysis for N-(3-chloroisobutyl) isatin Schiff bases (L16–L20) with DNA gyrase subunit B (PDB ID: 5CPH).

Ligand ID	L16	L17	L18	L19	L20
Conformations	2	5	3	1	1
RMSD from reference structure, Å	7.196	6.722	8.515	8.419	8.716
Binding energy, kcal/mol	-6.51	-6.82	-8.30	-8.31	-8.45
Inhibition constant, Ki	16.80 μ M	10.10 μ M	820.90 nM	812.51 nM	636.34 nM
Intermolecular energy, kcal/mol	-7.71	-8.01	-9.50	-9.50	-9.65
Total internal energy, kcal/mol	-12.16	-14.23	-14.93	-14.45	-14.22
Torsional free energy, kcal/mol	+1.19	+1.19	+1.19	+1.19	+1.19
Unbound energy, kcal/mol	-12.16	-14.23	-14.93	-14.45	-14.22

-8.30 kcal/mol), differing minimally in energetics, while fluorination led to a weaker, albeit distinct, improvement ($\Delta G = -6.82$ kcal/mol). These data outline a clear pattern: increasing the atomic mass of the halogen is accompanied by an increase in affinity, supporting the possible role of polarizability as an important factor for this type of bulky N-substituent.

Conformational analysis provides additional insight into the stability of the complex. The lowest RMSD values are observed for L17 (6.72 Å), indicating a more stable binding orientation and good repeatability of the poses. In contrast, halogens with larger atomic radii—Cl, Br, and I—form more heterogeneous geometric solutions with RMSDs in the range of 8.4–8.7 Å. This behavior suggests that the bulkier substituents induce a slight rearrangement of the ligand in the hydrophobic cavity, probably occupying a deeper position but with a wider range of permissible orientations. Although the geometric dispersion seems unfavorable, energetics gives it another meaning: these “more flexible” complexes showed the lowest docking-derived ΔG values and were therefore prioritized as the most promising compounds for further evaluation.

The number of conformations in the top cluster varies from five for L17 to only one for L19 and L20. This contrast reflects a different balance between stability and energy depth: fluorine provides a more homogeneous but weaker configuration, while heavy halogens lead to separate but extremely stable orientations. Intermolecular energy confirms this relationship: it increases in the direction $-H < -F < -Cl \approx -Br < -I$, reaching -9.65 kcal/mol for the iodinated analog. In the absence of variations in torsional energy, this component is decisive for the final affinity.

Compared with the previous series, the N-(3-chloroisobutyl) derivatives suggest a possible synergistic relationship between the bulk of the N-substituent and the polarizability of the halogen. While in the N-(2-chloroethyl) and N-(3-chloropropyl) derivatives the heavier halogens only partially compensated for the increased flexibility, here they were associated with improved predicted affinity, outperforming not only the corresponding non-alkylated analogs but also some of the smaller series. These results indicate that in the presence of a bulkier and hydrophobic N-substituent, the ligand adopts a more compact orientation in the hydrophobic pocket, in which π - σ , π -alkyl, and halogen interactions with residues such as Ile86, Ile102, and Leu103, assisted by

water-mediated hydrogen bonds, appear to contribute substantially to the predicted stabilization of the complex.

Compared to the previous series, the N-(3-chloroisobutyl) derivatives demonstrate a distinct synergy between the bulk of the N-substituent and the polarizability of the halogen. While in the N-(2-chloroethyl) and N-(3-chloropropyl) derivatives the heavier halogens only partially compensated for the increased flexibility, here they were associated with improved predicted affinity, outperforming not only the corresponding non-alkylated analogs but also some of the smaller series. These results indicate that in the presence of a bulkier and hydrophobic N-substituent, the ligand adopts a more compact orientation in the hydrophobic pocket, in which π - σ , π -alkyl, and halogen interactions with residues such as Ile86, Ile102, and Leu103, assisted by water-mediated hydrogen bonds, become the main stabilizing forces of the complex.

Despite the high energy stability, it should be noted that the single orientations reported for L19 and L20 suggest the need for confirmation by additional docking or, alternatively, computational iteration with different initial conditions. Such a check would clarify whether the reported values arise from a local minimum or from a truly stable and reproducible binding model.

The 2D interaction diagrams, shown in Fig. 6, illustrate the spatial arrangement and nature of the non-covalent contacts within the GyrB active site, offering visual confirmation of the structural factors governing ligand affinity and orientation.

Flexible docking analysis

Table 6 summarizes the subset of amino acid residues from the GyrB active site that were defined as flexible during docking calculations. The selection was limited to residues directly involved in ligand recognition and stabilization to allow realistic side-chain motion within the catalytic pocket while maintaining the overall rigidity of the protein backbone.

The flexible docking results for the 20 isatin derivatives showed a tendency to occupy the ATP-binding pocket in the docking model, with a large number of them showing spatial proximity to key ATP-binding-site residues. The most frequently involved amino acids were Ile86 and Ile102, which form the hydrophobic “seat” of the binding

Figure 6. Interaction maps of N-(3-chloroisobutyl) isatin Schiff bases (L16–L20) docked in the ATP-binding site of DNA gyrase subunit B (PDB ID: 5CPH).

Table 6. Key flexible residues in the ATP-binding site of GyrB (PDB ID: 5CPH) and their roles in ligand binding.

Residue	Position (chain A)	Residue type	Physicochemical nature	Role in ligand binding
Asn54	54	Polar, uncharged	Hydrophilic amide side chain; hydrogen-bond donor and acceptor	May participate in hydrogen bonding or water-mediated contacts with ligand carbonyl, azomethine, or heteroatom-containing groups; contributes to polar ligand recognition and helps define the hydrophilic region of the ATP-binding pocket.
Asp81	81	Acidic	Negatively charged, polar	Forms strong hydrogen bonds and ionic contacts with ligand carbonyl and azomethine groups.
Arg84	84	Basic	Positively charged	Participates in electrostatic stabilization and directional H-bonds within the catalytic core.
Glu85	85	Acidic	Polar, negatively charged	Provides additional ionic stabilization and supports the local hydrogen-bond network.
Ile86	86	Non-polar	Hydrophobic	Engages in π - σ and π -alkyl interactions, anchoring the ligand in the binding pocket.
Ile102	102	Non-polar	Hydrophobic	Strengthens van der Waals and dispersion interactions with the isatin ring system.
Arg144	144	Basic	Positively charged	Functions as a flexible gating residue; stabilizes ligand entry and maintains charge balance.

site and stabilize the isatin core through π - σ and π -alkyl interactions, as illustrated in Figs 2–5.

The polar residues Asp81 and Glu85 were predicted to participate in hydrogen bonds or water-mediated contacts in almost all derivatives. In some of the ligands (e.g., L09 and L13), additional engagement of Arg84 was observed, which is typical for molecules with a more pronounced dipole moment and the ability to form stabilizing ionic contacts.

Halogenated derivatives were characterized by enhanced polarizability and a larger contact area of the Cl, Br, and I atoms. The highest coverage of the active site was observed in the brominated and iodinated N-alkylated derivatives—usually with simultaneous contacts to Asp81, Ile86, and Ile102, and sometimes to Arg84.

The N-(3-chloroisobutyl)-substituted series (L16–L20) showed the best combination of stable hydrophobic anchoring and the presence of polar interactions. Despite the

larger steric bulk at the N1 position, the iodinated derivative (L20) retained a favorable predicted orientation toward Ile86 and Ile102, suggesting good adaptability of the isatin backbone to the spatial organization of the enzyme pocket.

The flexible docking analysis suggests that the studied isatin derivatives can be accommodated within the ATP-binding site of GyrB, with several compounds showing favorable predicted binding energies. The presence of Asp81 and Ile86 in almost all complexes suggests that these residues may contribute to ligand accommodation in the docking model, and the frequent participation of Arg84 and Ile102 indicates additional stability through π - σ and ionic interactions.

Overall, heavier halogens appeared to improve the predicted binding profile mainly in the N-alkylated series, whereas fluorination was more favorable in the non-alkylated series. These trends are consistent with published data in the literature on GyrB inhibitors, where Asp81, Arg84, and Ile86 are described as universal anchor positions for stabilizing the ligand in the ATP-binding site.

Docking-based structure–affinity relationship

Because no experimental antibacterial or enzymatic inhibition data were generated in the present study, the term structure–affinity relationship is used here to describe docking-derived trends in binding energy, calculated K_i values, and predicted interaction patterns, rather than experimentally confirmed structure–activity relationships. The analysis was therefore focused on identifying how systematic changes in halogen substitution and N1-alkylation influenced the predicted accommodation of the

isatin Schiff base scaffold within the ATP-binding pocket of GyrB. Particular attention was paid to the balance between polar anchoring, hydrophobic stabilization, halogen-associated contacts, and the torsional penalty introduced by N-chloroalkyl substituents.

The structure–affinity analysis of the studied isatin derivatives suggested a relationship between the electronic properties of the halogen substituents, the volume of the N-chloroalkyl group, and the affinity for the GyrB enzyme. The general trend in affinity of all halogenated and N-chloroalkylated derivatives is shown in Fig. 7, which presents a heatmap of binding energies for all 20 ligands docked in the ATP-binding pocket of GyrB. The heatmap visualizes the compensatory effect between halogen polarizability and N-alkyl chain length, showing that the fluorinated non-alkylated analog and selected brominated/iodinated N-alkylated derivatives had the most favorable docking-derived binding energies.

N1-alkylation altered the predicted binding profile by increasing ligand flexibility and changing the spatial reach of the scaffold within the ATP-binding pocket. The N-(2-chloroethyl) derivatives appeared to provide a favorable balance between size and flexibility, whereas extension to N-(3-chloropropyl) or N-(3-chloroisobutyl) increased the torsional penalty. In these bulkier series, the presence of more polarizable halogens, particularly bromine and iodine, was associated with improved docking-derived binding energies, suggesting that additional hydrophobic and dispersion-type contacts may partially compensate for the increased flexibility.

The docking-derived affinity pattern was not governed by halogen size alone but by the interaction between halogen substitution and the steric profile of the

Figure 7. Heatmap of binding free energies (ΔG , kcal/mol) for halogenated and N-chloroalkyl isatin Schiff base derivatives docked to the ATP-binding site of *Staphylococcus aureus* GyrB (PDB ID: 5CPH).

N1 substituent. In the non-alkylated series, the fluorinated derivative L02 showed the most favorable docking score among all ligands, suggesting that the small size and strong electron-withdrawing character of fluorine may optimize the electronic distribution of the isatin core without introducing steric strain. In contrast, heavier halogens did not further improve the predicted affinity in this series, most likely because the non-alkylated scaffold lacks sufficient steric extension to accommodate larger substituents without altering the preferred binding orientation.

In the N-alkylated series, the trend changed. Bromine was most favorable in the N-(2-chloroethyl) group, whereas iodine became more favorable in the N-(3-chloropropyl) and N-(3-chloroisobutyl) series. This suggests that heavier, more polarizable halogens may become advantageous only when the N1 substituent provides additional hydrophobic surface and spatial extension. Under these conditions, the larger halogens may contribute to improved van der Waals, π -alkyl, and halogen-associated contacts with hydrophobic residues such as Ile86, Ile102, and Leu103. Thus, the predicted affinity was context-dependent: fluorination favored the compact non-alkylated scaffold, whereas bromination and iodination favored bulkier N-alkylated analogs.

In the different series, the best-scoring ligands shared a similar binding pattern, which is characterized by the combined participation of polar and hydrophobic interactions in the active site. Polar bonds provide the orientation and anchoring of the isatin core, while hydrophobic and dispersion forces stabilize the complex and contribute to increasing the overall stability and affinity of the ligand. Water-mediated hydrogen bonds also play an important role, connecting the carbonyl and azomethine groups of the ligand to the surrounding amino acid network. This combination of polar stabilization and hydrophobic anchoring may explain the recurrent predicted binding pattern observed among the best-scoring isatin derivatives.

From a pharmacophore-oriented perspective, the best-scoring ligands shared several recurring structural features. The isatin carbonyl and azomethine region acted as the main polar recognition motif and was predicted to participate in direct or water-mediated interactions with polar residues such as Asp81, Asn54, Ser55, and Arg84. The fused aromatic isatin system and the pyridyl-imine fragment provided an extended π -surface capable of hydrophobic, π - σ , and π -alkyl contacts with Ile86, Ile102, and Leu103. The halogen substituent modulated the electronic character and polarizability of this aromatic system, whereas the N1-chloroalkyl group influenced the spatial reach, lipophilicity, and torsional flexibility of the ligand. Therefore, the predicted GyrB binding profile appears to depend on the coordinated contribution of four elements: a polar donor-acceptor region, an aromatic hydrophobic surface, a halogen-dependent electronic modifier, and an N1 substituent controlling steric accommodation.

Although the docking results cannot verify inhibitory potency, they provide a structural rationale for prioritizing selected derivatives for future GyrB inhibition assays.

Compounds such as L02, L09, L15, and L20 combined favorable docking scores with predicted interactions involving residues commonly associated with ligand accommodation in the GyrB ATP-binding pocket. These compounds may therefore be considered priority candidates for synthesis and biological evaluation. However, the observed differences in docking-derived binding energy should not be interpreted as confirmed differences in inhibitory activity, because enzyme inhibition depends not only on static binding pose but also on complex stability over time, solvation effects, protein flexibility, ligand permeability, and experimental target engagement.

The results indicate that the most favorable docking profiles were obtained when the electronic effect of the halogen substituent was compatible with the steric demand of the N1 group. Small and strongly electronegative fluorine was favorable for the compact non-alkylated scaffold, whereas heavier and more polarizable halogens were better tolerated in selected N-alkylated derivatives. This behavior suggests a compensatory relationship between electronic tuning and steric accommodation. However, this relationship was not linear across the entire ligand set. Instead, each N1-substituted series displayed a distinct halogen preference, indicating that optimization of isatin Schiff bases for GyrB binding should not rely on halogen size alone but on the combined effect of halogen polarizability, N1-substituent bulk, and preservation of polar contacts within the ATP-binding pocket.

Literature-based contextualization with known GyrB inhibitor binding features

The following section is intended as qualitative literature-based contextualization rather than direct benchmarking, because known GyrB inhibitors were not docked or experimentally tested under the same conditions in the present study. Fluoroquinolones (e.g., ciprofloxacin, levofloxacin, moxifloxacin) act by inhibiting the DNA gyrase-DNA complex, stabilizing the broken form of double-stranded DNA and blocking the supercoiling process. Although their primary target is the A subunit of the enzyme (GyrA), they also interact with GyrB through hydrogen and π - π contacts with amino acids such as Asp81, Arg84, Glu85, and Ile86 (Mustaev et al. 2014). These residues are the same as those involved in the stabilization of isatin Schiff bases in the present study. Therefore, the designed isatin derivatives are positioned in the same catalytic region, suggesting that the designed compounds may occupy a binding region that overlaps with functionally relevant GyrB inhibitor sites, although whether such compounds could retain activity against resistant strains remains to be experimentally investigated.

In the coumarin group of antibiotics, novobiocin is one of the first known GyrB inhibitors. It binds directly to the ATP-binding domain of the B subunit and blocks ATP hydrolysis by forming a stable complex with Asp81 and Arg84, reinforced by hydrophobic contacts with Ile86 and Ile102 (May et al. 2017). In the present study, the same

amino acids provide the main stabilization points for the halogenated and N-alkylated isatin derivatives, suggesting partial overlap in the predicted residue-contact pattern. Similar interactions have been observed in aminocoumarin compounds such as clomacin and coumeracin, where hydrogen bonds with Asp81 and Glu85, combined with π - σ contacts with Ile86, provide a stable enzyme-ligand complex (Vanden Broeck et al. 2019).

Among the newer molecular prototypes, benzamide inhibitors such as ETX0914 (zoliflodacin), GSK299423, and QPT-1 also target the ATP-binding pocket of GyrB and show high selectivity and activity against multidrug-resistant strains (Chan et al. 2015). In them, hydrogen bonds with Asp81 and Glu85, as well as hydrophobic contacts with Ile86 and Ile102, are crucial for affinity, which is partly consistent with the predicted interaction model for the isatin ligands.

In this context, the designed isatin Schiff bases appear to share selected interaction features with several well-studied classes of GyrB inhibitors, such as an electronically active π -system, as in fluoroquinolones; donor-acceptor centers, as in novobiocin; and the ability to hydrophobically anchor in the ATP-binding domain, similar to benzamide derivatives. This partial overlap supports further investigation of the isatin scaffold as a potential starting point for GyrB-targeted antibacterial design, but it does not establish inhibitory activity or resistance-overcoming capacity. However, the calculated binding energies (approximately -6.5 to -8.5 kcal/mol) indicate moderate affinity, characteristic of reversible non-covalent interactions and an initial stage of structural optimization. This suggests that the isatin core represents a promising structural template, but further modifications aimed at increasing polar complementarity and reducing torsional strain are needed to achieve more potent and selective inhibition.

Limitations

The present study should be interpreted within the limitations inherent to a docking-based *in silico* analysis. Although molecular docking is a useful tool for the preliminary prioritization of structurally related compounds and for generating structure-activity hypotheses, it does not provide direct evidence of antibacterial activity or confirmed enzymatic inhibition. Therefore, the predicted binding energies and inhibition constants reported here should be considered comparative estimates within the studied ligand series rather than experimentally validated measures of potency.

Only a focused set of 20 isatin Schiff base derivatives was investigated. This limited dataset was intentionally designed as a controlled substitution matrix to evaluate the combined effects of halogenation and N-chloroalkylation on the same core scaffold. However, the relatively small number of compounds restricts the broader generalization of the observed structure-affinity relationships to other isatin derivatives or chemically unrelated GyrB inhibitors.

Another important limitation is that the docking protocol was validated only by redocking of the co-crystal-

lized ligand. Although this approach supports the ability of the protocol to reproduce the experimentally observed binding orientation within the selected ATP-binding pocket, additional validation approaches, such as consensus docking, cross-docking, ligand-enrichment analysis, or comparison with larger sets of known active and inactive compounds, would further strengthen the robustness of the computational model. Furthermore, no molecular dynamics simulations were performed. As a result, the time-dependent stability of the predicted ligand-GyrB complexes, the flexibility of the binding pocket, solvent effects, and possible induced-fit rearrangements could not be evaluated. The reported interaction patterns should therefore be interpreted as static docking-derived binding models rather than dynamic descriptions of ligand behavior under physiological conditions.

Conclusion

The present *in silico* study outlines the main principles that govern the binding of isatin Schiff bases to the ATP-binding pocket of GyrB. Flexible docking suggested that all 20 ligands could be accommodated within the ATP-binding pocket dominated by hydrophobic contacts with Ile86, Ile102, and Leu103, assisted by hydrogen and electrostatic interactions with Asp81, Asn54, and Arg84. Systematic variation of the N1 substituent and the halogen in the aromatic core revealed clear SAR trends: fluorination was most favorable in the non-alkylated series, whereas heavier halogens, particularly bromine and iodine, were more beneficial in selected N-alkylated derivatives, and moderate N-alkylation may improve steric accommodation in some ligand series. These results highlight the necessary balance between electronic and steric effects and indicate that the combination of a moderately bulky N-substituent and a highly polarizable halogen was associated with more favorable predicted pocket occupancy. For the first time, a 4×4 matrix approach combining four halogens and four N-alkyls suggests possible synergistic relationships between polarizability and steric bulk, which have not been investigated in known classes of GyrB inhibitors. Thus, the study provides a new conceptual framework for the rational prioritization and subsequent experimental evaluation of isatin derivatives as potential GyrB-targeting antibacterial candidates.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

Regarding the use of AI in the preparation of this manuscript, the authors declare the following:

We would like to declare that artificial intelligence tools were used for linguistic refinement and improvement of the English language (grammar, clarity, and style). No artificial intelligence tools were used for data generation, data analysis, interpretation of results, scientific decision-making, or drawing conclusions. All scientific content, analyses, and interpretations were performed entirely by the authors.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.
